

NEW COVID-19 CORONAVIRUS INFECTION IN THE PRACTICE OF A NEONATOLOGIST AND PEDIATRICIAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13301994>

Annotation: The newborns from mothers with COVID-19 demonstrate the variability of clinical picture from asymptomatic course to severe respiratory failure. In the postneonatal period children have asymptomatic or mild course of a new coronavirus infection. It has been found that children with COVID-19, unlike adults, are unlikely to develop severe pneumonia, as well as conditions requiring intensive care and mechanical ventilation.

Key words: COVID-19, Coronavirus disease, children, asymptomatic, SARS-CoV-2.

Purpose of work. Widespread and very rapid spread of a new coronavirus infection in human The population has presented science and practical healthcare with a number of problems that require immediate solutions.

Materials and methods. At the same time, among the issues related to perinatology and pediatrics, the following were highlighted: does COVID-19 affect the course of pregnancy, childbirth and the fetus, the condition of the child in the neonatal period; what are the tactics of monitoring the baby if he is born from a mother with a positive COVID-19 status or with the mother's contact with infection; how to deal with the choice of feeding for the child in these cases; which of the children should be considered to be at high risk of severe course and unfavorable outcome of the disease. This review of data published in the period from January to April 25, 2020 in the open press or available as an electronic preprint on the official websites of peer-reviewed medical publications, international and national medical professional communities, as well as state regulatory bodies is devoted to these issues. It should be particularly noted that due to the limited number of observations, all the recommendations currently existing are of a temporary nature and may be revised.

Conclusion. In conclusion, we consider it appropriate to note that although there are currently no methods of specific therapy and prevention of a new coronavirus infection, humanity has very high hopes for an international research project to create vaccines against COVID-19, launched under the auspices of WHO, and a Global Joint Initiative. The program statement of the

Global Joint Initiative (04/24/2020) noted that, taking into account the human suffering, the devastating social and economic consequences of COVID-19, a strategy was announced and commitments were made to accelerate the development, production and fair distribution of new diagnostics, treatment, and vaccines to combat COVID-19.

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